

Echosounder and ROV rocky reef fish surveys: Step-by-step data collection and analysis guide

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This guide is included as supplementary data from the manuscript “Echosounder derived metrics from small-scale coastal surveys identify benthic rocky reef fish hotspots within the acoustic deadzone”. It is intended as a step-by-step guide for collecting echosounder and ROV data for detecting benthic rocky reef fish hotspots. Although we provide instructions on most aspects of data collection and analysis this guide will not provide all information necessary for individual projects and is intended simply as a reference manual for any researchers hoping to conduct similar studies. If you have specific questions please contact Darienne Lancaster (darienneolancaster@gmail.com).

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of study

The purpose of this research project was to develop an efficient method of identifying rocky reef fish hotspots in coastal regions using echosounder surveys. We focused on developing simple echosounder techniques that would be accessible to active acoustic novices to make echosounder surveys more feasible and understandable to a wider audience. A general understanding of active acoustic theory is still recommended before undertaking any echosounder surveys. We recommend the comprehensive active acoustic text by Simmonds et al. (2007) as a go to resource for gaining a basic understanding of active acoustic principles:

Simmonds, E. John, and David N. MacLennan. *Fisheries Acoustics: Theory and Practice*. 2. ed., Fish and Aquatic Resources Series 10. Oxford: Blackwell, 2007.

In this study we utilized nautical area scattering coefficient (NASC) as a proxy for fish biomass and investigated correlations between NASC and ROV detected benthic rocky reef fish density. We found a strong positive correlation between NASC values within 10m of the bottom and benthic fish density in the acoustic deadzone region in rocky, sloping habitats preferred by rocky reef fish species. Our best-fit rocky reef fish density model included NASC as a predictor and dramatically outperformed our other habitat-based models. This suggests that including NASC as a predictor of benthic rocky reef fish density can add substantially to regional distribution modelling.

Echosounder surveys can quickly identify areas with high near-bottom NASC values and this information can be used to develop regional maps of suspected high benthic rocky reef fish density for use by fishers (e.g. help avoid non-target rockfish species) or for selecting high fish density MPA locations. However, these echosounder surveys cannot identify fish species, diversity, abundance, or biomass and should only be used as a general guide for locating likely high benthic fish density areas. Additional groundtruthing is required using visual methods (e.g. ROV, drop camera, divers, hook-and-line) to determine species composition if this data is to be used for more quantitative assessments of rocky reef fish abundance or biomass. It is our hope that the ease and efficiency of these echosounder surveys will allow smaller organizations to collect detailed regional data that is often missing from coastwide surveys and use it to inform future rocky reef fish survey work or local fisheries management.

1.2. Purpose of guide

We provide step-by-step guidance on how to collect echosounder and ROV survey data in the field, how to calibrate acoustic instruments, how to process video and acoustic data in EventMeasure and Echoview software, and how to analyze annotated and exported data in R.

This guide is not meant to be an exhaustive how-to for all echosounder survey projects but we hope that by sharing some tips and tricks and difficulties we encountered we can make the process of beginning echosounder surveys more efficient for future researchers. If you have further questions contact Darienne Lancaster (darienneolancaster@gmail.com).

1.3. Software, equipment, and crew requirements

Software

- Visual Acquisition (comes with Biosonic echosounders)
- Echoview software (variable price subscription (~\$3000 - \$50,000 USD) – annual, multiyear, permanent, and student licenses available). These methods could be applied using an open-source software like Echotype but more advanced knowledge of coding and echogram properties would be required.
- QGroundControl (free – for operating BlueROV)
- Navionics (annual subscription) – alternate gps softwares will work
- EventMeasure (SeaGIS subscription – annual, student, permanent available) Other video annotation softwares like Biigle also work but we provide guidance for EventMeasure specifically.
- ImageJ (free)
- VLC (free)
- R (open-source)
- GitHub (optional - free)

Equipment

- Research vessel (used 24ft aluminum with single 115hp engine (Figure 1))
- Biosonic Scientific Split Beam echosounder (38 and 200kHz transducers (Figure 2, 3, 4)).
 - o Echosounder (~ \$5000), 200kHz transducer (~\$19,000), 38kHz transducer (~\$25,000)
- Custom mount for transducers (vessel specific –custom manufactured (Figure 2, 3))
- 38.1mm tungsten carbide calibration sphere
- BlueROV from Blue Robotics with four lights (Figure 5) –
 - o ROV (~\$8000 USD)
 - o Batteries (~\$600 USD) - minimum of 4 batteries recommended
- 10cm scaling lasers (Figure 5)
- Field laptops x2 (Figure 4)
- Harddrives x2 plus more for backup
- Lead weight/cannonball (15lb)
- Fishing rod and line
- Downrigger (optional)

Figure 1. Research vessel used for echosounder and ROV surveys.

Figure 2. 200kHz (smaller) and 38kHz (larger) transducers attached to custom welded boat mount.

Figure 3. Transducers mounted to side of research vessel.

Figure 4. Cabin set up on research vessel. Orange pelican case contains echosounder. Laptop on right is connected to BlueROV. Vessel equipped with extra exterior wheel so vessel operator could steer from outside cabin for better communication between ROV deckhand and vessel operator.

Figure 5. BlueROV with four lights and scaling lasers at bottom.

Crew

- ROV operator
- Biosonic echosounder operator
- Vessel operator
- Deckhand (deploys ROV, sets cannonball/clump weight, retrieves ROV, helps with map tracks/data recording)
- Additional crew is helpful if space/personnel allow

NOTE: We recommend having one person dedicated to each job to ensure consistency across data collection. Each person is responsible for quite a few jobs so developing a system and checklist for each position is helpful and dedicating a full day to practicing will ensure quality data collection.

2. Field Data Collection

2.1. Site Selection

Sites were selected at random from a rocky reef habitat model created in ArcGIS using substrate data from a DFO open-source layer (20m shallow substrate model) and an open source 20m x 20m digital elevation model.

Data sources:

<https://open.canada.ca/data/en/dataset/7b4fef7e-7cae-4379-97b8-62b03e9ac83d>

<https://open.canada.ca/data/en/dataset/b100cf6c-7818-4748-9960-9eab2aa6a7a0>

The model selected all depths less than 100m based on the length of our ROV tether, slope between 5-50 degrees as rockfish prefer some bottom relief but split-beam echosounder acoustic deadzones become too large after 50 degree slopes are reached, and rock habitat as rockfish preferentially select rocky habitat. Sites were spaced a minimum of one kilometer apart to ensure independence and 100m transects were performed three times from deep to shallow where surface conditions allowed (e.g. low current/wave height).

2.2. Equipment Checklists

2.2.1. Vessel and Departure Checklist

	Boat Checks
	Radio working/on channel 16
	Engines working
	Enough fuel
	Anchor on board
	Lines attached
	Bumpers in
	GPS/Radar (if available) working
	Running lights working
	Horn working
	First Aid/Safety Checks
	First Aid Kit onboard
	First Aid binder onboard
	PFDs for all passengers
	Heaving line/safety ring located
	Parbuckle lines available
	Boat orientation completed
	EPIRB/InReach onboard
	Water onboard
	Snack/Lunch bag onboard
	Gear Checklist
	Field Documentation
	Datasheets + Pencil
	White board/markers
	erasers for white board
	Clip Board
	Ipad with Navionics on it
	External hard drive
	Echosounder

	38kHz transducer
	200kHz transducer
	Mounting pole
	Blue mounting platform
	Biosonic Multi-Plexing cable that connects two transducers
	Biosonic Cable that connects to the multi-plexing cable to surface unit
	Surface Unit (Orange Case)
	Ethernet Cord
	AC power cord
	Laptop (with Visual Acquisition Software) and charger
	Echoview Dongle
	2x 15ft extension cords
	Biosonics
	GPS unit
	Pin for securing the mounting pole to boat
	Chopstick (for attaching GPS to mounting pole)
	Zap straps
	Rubber twist gear ties
	Wrenches (ones for all bolts on transducer and a crescent wrench)
	Measuring tape reel
	2x microfibre towels
	Silicone spray
	Extra screws, bolts and washers
	BlueROV
	Downrigger with line
	YSI meter
	Sharpies
	Electrical tape
	BlueROV
	ROV batteries
	ROV tether
	ROV laptop + charger
	ROV controller
	ROV GPS puck
	ROV comms box + ethernet cable
	ROV tracker (receiver and transmitter)
	Clump weight line + Clump Weight + rubber zip ties
	ROV vacuum pump
	Star Oddis

2.2.2. Pre-Deployment Checklist

Boat/Data Management	
	Depth sounder turned off
	Site Selected on Navionics
	100m transect drawn and named in Navionics (e.g. T0234)
	Transect 1 - Biosonic
	Transect 2 - Biosonic and ROV running at same time
	Transect 3 - Biosonic
	Final check that all items were recorded on data sheet (photo of datasheet)
	All files named correctly in correct folders for Navionics/Biosonic/ROV
Biosonic	
	Transducers oriented with cables at stern
	Transducers lined up with pole measurement lines
	200 and 38 transducers connected in Biosonic
	GPS connected (external GPS set to 38400 BAUD)
	Harddrive connected/Sub folder created for site (e.g. T0234)
	Transect named correctly (e.g. 0234_T1_Biosonic_20230726)
	Maximum speed 5knots
	Start/Stop times and depth recorded for each transect
	Fish school waypoints flagged with appropriate names (e.g. whatever Navionics calls them)
ROV	
	Fresh battery (~16volts)
	Passed leak check (hold at 10psi for 15 min)
	Pressure calibrated
	Propeller check (visual and air)
	StarOddi secured
	Tracker secured ROV/transmitter secured to boat/powered on
	Harddrive connected to laptop/subfolder created for site
	Biosonic recording during ROV deployment/named appropriately
	Video ON: Site name/date recorded with whiteboard before deploying
	Clump weight secured
	Rubber zip ties ready
	Video Off: Site name/date recorded with whiteboard after deploying
	ROV survey named appropriately on harddrive (e.g. 234_T2_ROV_20230726)
End of Day Checks	
	Rinse transducers and ROV
	To Charge:
	Tablet
	ROV Laptop
	Biosonic Laptop

	ROV batteries
	Backup Harddrives
	Transfer datasheets to folder at cabin/make sure all photographed

2.3. Setting up Navionics Routes

Once the site has been selected you will need to create a route to guide the boat when conducting surveys. Echosounders work best running perpendicular to bottom relief so try to set transects deep to shallow running straight up a slope. Running even slightly parallel to slopes creates very large sidelobe interference areas on echograms, especially on the 38kHz transducer.

Creating a Route/Track in Navionics App

Click 'Route' > 'Manual' (*prior to this, you may have to stop the route if one is already running)

Name the Route (e.g. NS01_T1 for NootkaSound Site 1 and Transect 1)

Press and hold a place on the map until a pink dot appears. This will be your starting point.

Press and hold another point on the map to begin creating the route.

If you press white arrow on the left side of the screen, a sidebar menu can be extended and retracted. This menu shows you the distances between points.

Based on parameters outlined in Tschersich, P., and W. Gaeuman. 2019. Hydroacoustic survey of black rockfish abundance and distribution operational plan for the Kodiak Management Area, 2020-2022. Alaska Department of Fish and Game, Division of Commercial Fisheries, Regional Operational Plan ROP.CF.4K.2019.04, Kodiak.

Resetting Units in Navionics

Ensure Navionics units are correct (default is nautical miles (NM) not km).

1. Press the 'Menu' button on the bottom of the screen
2. Go to 'Settings'
3. Select 'Units'
4. Change the units you are interested in altering

Recording Tracks

When conducting the surveys (T1, T2, T3) make sure you record your tracks to be able to assess how much the track deviated from the original route. To do this, hit the start button on the main screen of the app at the beginning of each transect, once complete hit stop and save. Go to the menu>routes to save the track with the appropriate name (e.g. NS01_T1, NS01_T2).

2.4. Setting up and Connecting the Transducer

The transducer head must be in the water before it is turned on and any data is collected. Turning the transducer on when it is not submerged will cause damage to the echosounder.

Placing the Transducer Head in the Water

1. Place transducer heads onto a protective surface on the boat deck (e.g., foam mat). Ensure the four bolts securing the blue platform to the transducer heads are fully tightened.
2. Bolt the blue platforms on the transducer heads to the blue attachment end on the mount/pole. Try to use these 1-2 bolts to secure the transducer head so that it will point downwards into the water without rotating.
3. Remove the red caps on the transducer head and cable, screwing them together tightly.
4. Have two people carefully lift the transducer heads and pole, placing the head into the water.
5. Secure the pole to the side of the boat with the pin.
6. Ensure there is no wobble in transducer pole as this will reduce the quality of your echogram data. Use ropes, etc... to stabilize pole to avoid movement. Drive very slowly to avoid putting strain on cables, pole, and transducer.

Note: Transducer cables should face the stern to avoid tension while driving. Ensure you know the orientation of your echosounders so you can specify which direction was forward later on in Echoview.

2.5. GPS and Battery Setup

1. Mount the GPS directly to the top of the transducer pole. Secure with a zip tie. NOTE: GPS should be directly above transducers for most accurate tracking. If it is not make a note of the distance the GPS is from transducers to update in Echoview during data processing.
2. Connect the GPS to the orange Biosonic case
3. Plug the AC power cord into the Inverter on the boat.

2.5.1. Troubleshooting GPS

In some instances VisAcq will not be able to register the GPS unit. To troubleshoot:

1. Make sure GPS is plugged into the right port on surface unit which is the Input External GPS
2. Set Baud Rate to 38400
 - Data collection configuration > Sensors > Baud rate
 - Set Sensor Update Rate to Automatic: based on ping rate

2.6. YSI Readings

1. Place the YSI meter sensor ~1 meter below the water's surface. Wait for the readings to stabilize and record the conductivity (salinity) and temperature readings. Both temperature and salinity impact how sound travels in water. Record the salinity, temperature, date, time, and associated echogram filename.

2.7. Surface Unit/Visual Acquisition Start Up

Steps for powering up the surface unit and beginning data collection.

1. Open the surface unit and ensure the main power is switched to 'OFF.'
2. Check that mode is set to 'Manual.'
3. Remove the black cap from the black cable and attach it to the surface unit.
4. Connect the power cable
5. Connect the GPS to the surface unit.
6. Turn the main power 'ON' on the surface unit.

7. Wait 90 seconds for a beep.
 - You should see Main Power, Awake, Ethernet and Ping light up
8. On the laptop, launch Visual Acquisition.
9. Press the 'Initialize' button.
10. Press the 'Configure' Button and choose your settings (see details in "4. Visual Acquisition Settings")
11. Press 'Start All' to begin pings and data collection once the boat is at the route starting position. NOTE: ensure the boat GPS, depth sounder, is turned off (if left on, it will leave streaks on the echogram)

2.7.1. Visual Acquisition Settings: Active Collection for Mobile Surveys

When the 'Configure' button is pressed in Visual Acquisition, you will be given the opportunity to select certain settings. Notes sections in this guide are summaries of important information found in the Visual Acquisition (VA) manual. View the manual for further details.

DTX Scientific Echosounder Settings (p. 51 of the VA manual)

Parameter	Suggested Settings	Comments
Ping Rate (pps)	5 - 10	Slow down ping rate for slow moving vessel, if vessel speed increases speed up ping rate.
Transmit Power Reduction Level (dB)	0	Reduce transmit power in very shallow areas (use -10dB for this).

Transmit/Receive (p. 56 of the VA manual)

Parameter	Suggested Settings	Comments
Acoustic Mode	Active Transmission	This causes the transducer to ping and listen for returning pings, passive means that the transducer is just listening. Passive data files can help determine how much background noise there is and Echoview can create a filter.
Transmit Pulse Duration (ms)	0.3-0.5	The shorter the pulse duration the better vertical resolution (e.g. separation between targets and the bottom), the tradeoff is you'll get less information out of those echoes and less certainty about the size of those targets. Multiplexing with two different settings can help with this.
Start Range (m)	0	Must include the top 1m to get the transmit pulse signature. In deeper areas you might need to set your range window deeper.
End Range	Survey specific.	Setting the end range 2.5 times the bottom depth will give you valuable information about the bottom type. If this information is

		not needed, then set your end range to be deeper than the deepest part of your survey area.
Calibration Correction (dB)	0	Based on your calibration test, can be added after data collection in post processing. Make sure you do a calibration test before and after your survey. See section 2.9.3 and 2.9.4 for calibration instructions.
Data collection Threshold Level (dB) ³	-130 (default)	This sets collection for all sizes of targets, setting to -130 is preferred.
Sampling Rate (Hz) ⁴	41667	Lowering the sampling rate can allow you to ping deeper but you lose vertical resolution, not recommended.

Notes

- Choppy water mitigation: In choppy water you'll get a wavy bottom artefact from the boat going up and down. This isn't usually a problem. Side to side rocking is an issue. This causes the beam to go off transect. Consider running transects into the waves rather than broad side to the waves. Minimizing roll (side to side) is more important than minimizing pitch (up and down). To avoid noise, you can put the transducer further in the water or slow down. Not much you can do about pitch and roll in settings once you've collected the data, need to control with weather and boat driving.
- The Data Collection Threshold (DCT) is the minimum echo level that can be recorded on a data file. Therefore, selecting a higher threshold truncates the recorded data irreversibly. The manual recommends that if you are unsure what to set the DCT at, to use the default.
- The Sampling Rate sets the sampling rate for digitizing the analog acoustic return echo inside the transducer. Two lower settings are possible: 20,833.5 and 10,416.75
 - Selecting these lower settings allows the DTX to collect data to a longer range (max. 1000 m) but may also limit post processing options.
 - If using these lower settings, you must also select the correct transmit pulse duration:
 - 0.4 ms for a 20,833.5 Hz rate.
 - 0.8 ms for a 10,416.75 Hz rate.
- Sample Size is the length of each digital sample. Sample Size depends on the sound velocity and sampling rate.
 - Samples per Pulse Duration = greater detail in one ping.

Sensors/Mounting (p. 59 of the VA manual)

Parameter	Suggested Settings	Comments
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GPS Detected	<i>(fixed)</i> Yes	Best to use external GPS for mapping, double check that it is working before conducting survey
NMEA Sentences Detected	<i>(fixed)</i> GPGGA, GPGSA, GPGSV, GPRMC	
Transducer Depth (m)		Set the depth to the how deep the transducer face is under the water surface.
Sensor Detected	<i>(fixed)</i> Yes	
Sensor Orientation	Down-looking	
Transducer Connector Position (deg)	0° if transducer cable connectors are pointing to the bow	180° if transducer cable connectors are pointing to the stern (this alignment recommended to reduce drag on transducer cables)
Advanced... Enable Synchronized Mode	Check/Uncheck depending on enviro.	See notes
Temperature Sensor Detection	<i>(fixed)</i> No	

Notes

If Synchronized Mode is enabled, the orientation of the sensor is read after every ping. If unchecked, the orientation of the sensor is read independently from when the pings occur.

Enabling synchronized mode when pinging to long ranges (i.e., great depths) may reduce noise.

Do not enable synchronized mode when pinging to very short ranges as it may slow the ping rate since the orientation of the sensor needs to be read frequently.

Single Echo Detection, AutoTrack Detection and Reporting (p. 64-66 in the VA Manual)

Single Echo (a.k.a. “single targets”, “point targets”, “single-target echoes”, “single scatterers” etc.) detection needs to be enabled if you would like to also enable auto tracking. This is required for conducting a calibration.

Data Logging (pg.72-75 in the VA Manual)

Parameter	Settings	Comments
Data Logging Folder	Select path to desired folder	Choose project folder on the desktop.

File Prefix	[site]_[Transect#]_[YYYYMMDD]	929_T1_28072021
Timestamp/Sequence Number	Timestamp selected	
File suffix	(blank)	
File Duration (min)	30	
File Cutting Mode	Elapsed Time	
Create DT4 Data Files	Checked	
Create DTB Bottom Pick Files	Unchecked	
Create ICES HAC Data File	Checked	

Summary

Always check the following configuration settings when collecting new data...

- Transmit/Receive > End Range [2.5x bottom range]
- Environment > Temperature [from YSI reading]
- Environment > Salinity [YSI reading]
- Data Logging > File Prefix [[site]_[transect#]_[date]]

If switching from a very shallow site to a deep site...

- Sensors/Mounting > Advanced > Enable Synchronized Mode

2.7.2. Additional Notes on Visual Acquisition

Marking an Event

It is possible to Mark an Event on the echogram when the echosounder is collecting data. Press the blue “Mark Event” button and Visual Acquisition will allow you to write a note associated with the number of the ping when the button was pressed. This may be useful for noting, the start and finish of transects or the locations of points of interest like fish schools.

Viewing Echograms in Visual Acquisition

Echograms in Visual Acquisition can be viewed in 3 different ways: raw/detection/both (Shortcut: F5). ‘Raw’ displays the TS/Sv echogram. ‘Detection’ will display the brown bottom detection line and fish tracks alone. Visual acquisition also allows you to zoom into echograms. Se VA Manual p. 12 to interpret target colouration.

Left to Right: Raw, Detection, Both displays

Display Threshold

The Display Threshold can be adjusted to change the amount of data displayed on the screen. This does not change the amount of data collected. Decreasing the display threshold will increase the amount of data displayed. (Shortcut to decrease: Shift + F3)

Starting Surveys

When all the above steps have been completed...

- Check again that the boat depth sounder, GPS is off.
- Press 'Go' on the Navionics Route when the boat is at the proper starting place, and you are ready to start surveying.
- Press 'Start All' on the surface unit.
- Conduct surveys travelling at ~3 knots.

Ending Surveys & Travelling Between Survey Sites

To end surveys, follow the steps in "3. Surface Unit/Visual Acquisition Start Up" or on the surface unit lid in reverse. If you are conducting more surveys elsewhere, you do not need to disconnect the battery, GPS, or transducer from the surface unit.

When travelling (fast) between sites, remove the transducer head from the water by unpinning the mount/pole and lying the pole and transducer head securely on the boat deck. The transducer head should be placed on a cushioned surface, not knocking against anything.

Post-Trip Wrap Up

- Take the battery from the boat if it needs to be charged.
- Plug in Ipad, laptop for charging and future use.
- Rinse Transducer Head in freshwater.
- Place ROV in bucket in fresh water and let it run its cleaning cycle
- Move the data from the folder on the desktop to the appropriate project folder.

2.8. BlueROV

2.8.1. ROV pre-deployment

- Clean o-rings and seals with kimwipes before each deployment. Even a hair can cause a large leak underwater.
- Vacuum check battery and electronics compartment with a handheld vacuum pump before deploying. Vacuum should hold at 10psi for 15min. Newer blue ROVs are likely threaded so they are less likely to leak but proper o-ring care is essential to avoid flooding.
- Run a pre-deployment motor check to ensure the controls are working as expected. Arm the ROV and have deckhand put their hands in front of propellers to ensure air is blowing in the correct direction for the controls. This avoids botched deployments with the ROV in the water and not responding as you expect.

2.8.2. ROV Deployment

- Deploy ROV beside boat, drive ROV slightly away and in front of vessel before descending. Set heading with stabilize mode and have driver/deckhand confirm ROV is facing the right way. Descend fast (75% gain) to minimize drift. Reduce gain to 50% ~20ft before reaching expected bottom depth to reduce risk of ROV bottom contact.
- Once ROV is on bottom, surface tenders attached 15lb clump weight on down rigger with rubber zipties, lower clump weight to ~20ft below boat to keep tether out of motors (See ROV deployment figure). We found using the clump weight all the way to bottom would drag the ROV around underwater and cause loss of control. Having a loose tether with short clump

weight near the surface almost completely eliminated drag on ROV.

- Once ROV is on bottom drive ROV following transect heading at 50% gain (this adds a bit of power for pulling loose cable through water column).
- Discontinue dives once battery voltage is below 13V DC to avoid losing power while underwater.

2.8.3. ROV Troubleshooting tips

- If the ROV tether gets pulled a bit underwater sometimes the stabilize mode will get confused and the ROV will start to drive crooked. You can switch back to manual and then hit stabilize again and this will correct the crooked orientation.
- Occasionally the ROV will reset its controls to the factory defaults or some other combination of controls. It is a good idea for anyone using the ROV to know how to reset the controls to the desired setting within the BlueROV set up section and how to run a basic calibration.
- Occasionally the battery will not connect properly and you won't get video footage. Always wait to fully place the battery and vacuum check it until video feed is working to avoid having to take the battery in and out multiple times.
- The surface unit can overheat in extreme temperatures (e.g. 40 degree C) and this will cause the video to cut out. Try to keep shaded or cool with a breeze or stop deploying once the surface unit is too hot.

- The 10cm sizing lasers are very difficult to get on fish without very calculated turning and following of fish which **is** a bit counter to the design of a straight consistent speed transect. The lasers can work well to size within densely packed schools and work best at a 10 degree downward angle depending on the slope of your bottom. Sizing lasers are also helpful for determining average field of view and visibility even if they are not great at getting fish sizes. There are always some issues with fish chasing the lasers. In particular, Kelp Greenlings and Copper Rockfish frequently follow lasers.
- The ROV video will often cut out and stop recording while at the surface. It's very important to make sure your video is actually recording once the ROV is in the water as it will often restart. You usually have to click the button twice for it to actually start recording.

2.8.4. Additional ROV comments

- Rechargeable batteries were good for 3-4 10min transects plus having it running on deck while disarmed for several hours. Keeping ROV sheltered from sun under a blanket/jacket successfully kept it cool from the sun. Batteries typically recharge in about 1 hour.
- We were able to deploy to ~230ft/70m using the loose tether method, beyond that depth we struggled getting the ROV to the bottom without losing some control. Maybe lowering the clump weight lower in the water column in this situation could help get deeper and maintain control. 100m tether is a depth limiting factor so could order a longer tether. However, ROV may not have enough power at very deep depths to drive straight transects.
- Driving transects in the direction of current or wind helps small boats stay in control and not drag the ROV. If it is possible to create transects in the field with consideration of wind/current direction transect success will be much higher. We did not operate in strong wave conditions and tried to go to calm areas as much as possible. We were able to operate in moderate swell (~1-2m). Instead of picking predefined transects we used a habitat model of all available rockfish habitat in the area and picked sites immediately before surveying based on wind and current conditions at the time, this gave a great deal of flexibility which helped avoid trying to deploy in bad conditions. We also started surveying early to catch calm morning weather and avoid midday heat and we planned surveys to start in exposed sites early and move to more sheltered areas throughout the day as the winds pick up.

2.8.5. ROV file management

- **It is helpful to create a separate working directory for each survey site for saving the video files (see example photos below).** We would take a short video of a site slate that included the site name, date, and water temperature as well as any notes. This slate video would be saved to the same folder as the deployment video. After the ROV was back onboard we would rename the video with the site name and data immediately since the default names are not very descriptive. You will need to rename the associated .ass file (records depth, heading, etc...) with the same name for it to load in VLC media viewer.

This PC > Haoom_Lanc2 (D:) > Biosonic_ROV_2023 > Nootka_Aug2023 > ROV >

Name	Date modified	Type	Size
NS01	8/10/2023 5:11 PM	File folder	
NS02	8/10/2023 1:21 PM	File folder	
NS03	8/10/2023 2:00 PM	File folder	
NS04	8/10/2023 3:09 PM	File folder	
NS05	8/11/2023 9:30 AM	File folder	
NS06	8/11/2023 10:50 AM	File folder	
NS07	8/11/2023 11:33 AM	File folder	
NS08	8/11/2023 12:17 PM	File folder	
NS09	8/11/2023 1:04 PM	File folder	
NS10	8/11/2023 1:43 PM	File folder	
NS11	8/11/2023 2:40 PM	File folder	

- The following items are helpful to have displayed on the ROV window during operation and for post-processing/analysis:

- Temperature 1 = internal temperature of ROV (once internal temperature is over 65 degrees it may shut down)
- Temperature 2 = underwater/air temperature
- Camera tilt is important for keeping video field of view consistent across transects
- Pilot gain controls speed of ROV and is also important for controlling consistency of transect data
- Heading is essential for keeping boat and ROV moving in the same direction. Stabilize mode will hold ROV on this heading but a lot of drag on the tether can knock it off course. Can always take stabilize off, reorient to desired heading and then reset stabilize during a transect.
- Lights should be consistent across transects but can be turned off while at the surface to save battery.

2.9. Echosounder Calibration

Field calibration is typically required at the start and end of all surveys, whenever you change survey locations (e.g. moving to a new study region), and periodically throughout the survey if conducted over a prolonged period (e.g. >2-3 weeks). Calibration should be performed in a deep area with calm water and no current. We moored our research vessel at the end of a quiet dock in deep water (>10m).

2.9.1. Field Calibration using Visual Acquisition

1. Ping Rate

Specific Ping Rate should be in between 10-15 pps

- Remember that when you ping more slowly the target needs to be held in the beam quadrant longer to get a good number of echoes

2. Transducer Mode

- Make sure it is in split beam mode
- Check the calibration date – this is the date that the transducer was last calibrated at the factor. This should happen once a year.

3. Transmit/Receive

- Acoustic mode: active transmission

- Transmit Pulse Duration: should be between 0.4 and 0.5
- Start range: 0.5
- End range: 6.5
 - These need to be set within a range in which the calibration sphere will be detected
 - The calibration sphere should be 5-10 below the transducer for a 200kHz transducer and 10-15m below for a 38kHz transducer.
- The calibration correction will be calculated with the calibration – leave it at 0 for now.
- Data collection threshold: -130
 - This is the full threshold

4. Sensors/Mounting

- Transducer depth: the depth of the face of the transducer below the surface of the water

5. Environment

- Temperature: needs to be within a degree of the water temperature (need accurate temp measurement) because all other temperature measurements will be measured off of this
 - Check freshwater box if in fresh water
 - If in salt water you need to add the salinity or add 32 parts per thousands can be used if you don't have this measurement

6. Bottom Detection

- This doesn't need to be enabled for calibration data but it is useful for separating echoes from the bottom when you're doing your analysis so you can check this box but need to know appropriate setting values

7. Echo Detection

- You need to enable this if you are analysing the calibration data in VisAcq

- If you are using Echoview, you don't need to have it checked

Max SD Split-Beam Angles (deg): 6

Max beam compensation: -6

- This is how far from the centre of the beam you are going to allow echoes to be recognized

Save Configuration

- save_as
- set a directory to save the calibration setting to make it easier and consistent in the future.

2.9.2. Calibration sphere setup

Figure 6. Diagram of calibration sphere technique. Calibration is best performed with one person controlling fishing rod and two other people holding adjustment monofilament lines to help position sphere in transducer beam. A) Transducer in water angled outward at ~1 degree. B) Fishing rod suspending calibration sphere 5-10m below water surface in transducer beam. Red box – enlargement of calibration sphere tied with multiple strands of monofilament line. Calibration can be performed on vessel or other stable platform in deep water (>15m recommended).

1. Suspending calibration sphere: Suspend 38.1mm Tungsten carbide calibration sphere using monofilament fishing line. Sphere should be suspended using a crisscrossing pattern in the monofilament line and attached to a fishing rod for lowering into the transducer beam. We also recommend attaching additional “marionette” lines to the sphere to allow for side to side and forward/backward manipulation within the beam. NOTE: avoid large knots in monofilament line where possible as these will be picked up in the transducer beam and can contaminate calibration results.
2. Soaping: Apply a biodegradable no-phosphorus soap to the face of the transducer just a tiny bit to break up the surface tension so we don't get bubbles same for the calibration sphere

2. Taking temperature: Take a temperature measurement by the transducer within a degree Celsius
3. Coming to Ambient temperature: Allow the calibration sphere and the transducer to come to ambient water temperature before doing the calibration data
4. Tilted transducer: The transducer should be slightly tilted away from you (Tilt angle ~ 1 degree) so its easier to get the calibration sphere under the transducer.
5. Crew requirements: It is recommended you have at least 3 people manipulating the calibration sphere and one person available to monitor the calibration data in VisAqua.

It is important to get the calibration sphere in all 4 quadrants and especially directly in the center of the beam in the cross of the bullseye. If you cannot take measurements in one or more quadrants or the bullseye you may get a false indication that there is a calibration problem.

Logging data

- Get the bullseye display up and the oscilloscope graph, and a regular echograph
- Lower the sphere into the beam. It is usually easier to get the sphere in the beam shallower and then slowly move it deeper while keeping it in the beam. It is quite hard to get the sphere into the beam at depth. The sphere should show up as a very strong continuous target in the echogram, as you lower it you should see the target lowering in depth on the echogram.

- Collect 2500-3500 echoes total (spread echoes evenly between the 4 quadrants and the bullseye crosshairs)

Moving calibration sphere

- Move the cal sphere in and out of all quadrants in a spiralling motion
- It is always better to have too many echoes so collect more than you think are necessary across the entire area of the bullseye.

2.9.3. Visual Acquisition calibration offset calculation

Visual Acquisition calibration provides a faster and more straightforward calibration check than Echoview calibration but it is only useful for assessing if calibration offsets are required for your data. We recommend processing your calibration data in Echoview for more detailed results and Echoview calibration is required if you need to apply TS and Sv offset values to your .ecs files. We provide further details on how to perform calibrations in Echoview in section 2.9.4.

Open Visual Acquisition

- Playback > open data file > select desired file

- Make sure you are using the data from the transducer of interest if both transducers are pinging

- Outline the area of the echogram that you believe to be the sphere
- Be as narrow as possible to avoid as much noise as possible without missing crucial data

- In this you can see that there is noise from the surface so I would ensure done of the top strip is included
- Next step is to select the [Raw data/ Detection / Both] which is the red graph line

- Right click on the graph
- Select Echo Summary Report

- Select Export Echo Data
- Set parameters
 - Field delimiter: default
 - File Extension: .csv

- Select Save to files
 - Select appropriate name

Open file into Excel:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	Index	Ping Time	Ping Num	Target Id	Range (m)	X Angle (°)	Y Angle (°)	dSD X	SD Y	Echo Leve	Target Str	Bn
2	1	2023-05-2	4	1	0.442583	0.266457	0.82441	0.07747	0.499476	-67.1313	-66.9512	-0.09008
3	2	2023-05-2	4	2	1.239231	-6.60854	-2.00039	0.515414	0.284455	-56.7827	-45.3408	-5.72093
4	3	2023-05-2	4	3	1.664111	4.184083	-0.18649	2.398539	0.387971	-49.6838	-45.4739	-2.10496
5	4	2023-05-2	4	4	2.46076	-1.64868	-0.83351	0.899542	1.70488	-70.5939	-69.7748	-0.40955
6	5	2023-05-2	5	1	0.442583	0.274331	0.769291	0.081753	0.511084	-67.2839	-67.1238	-0.08005
7	6	2023-05-2	5	2	1.540188	3.779744	-0.36014	3.312086	0.29452	-48.2087	-44.7488	-1.72994
8	7	2023-05-2	6	1	0.442583	0.297953	0.745669	0.097014	0.505583	-67.18	-67.0252	-0.07738
9	8	2023-05-2	6	2	1.203825	-0.53617	-3.46273	2.451233	0.553505	-49.4463	-46.4996	-1.47336
10	9	2023-05-2	6	3	1.858847	-0.21611	-0.25883	0.356619	0.208766	-46.2896	-46.2623	-0.01364
11	10	2023-05-2	6	4	2.974155	-4.55729	-3.07141	0.969269	3.606129	-70.027	-62.7784	-3.62429
12	11	2023-05-2	6	5	3.682288	-0.92449	-2.4876	0.577789	1.63452	-66.202	-64.5117	-0.84514
13	12	2023-05-2	7	1	0.442583	0.297953	0.777165	0.070074	0.51215	-67.2243	-67.058	-0.08313
14	13	2023-05-2	7	2	1.451671	0.331417	-2.43347	0.987282	0.59063	-46.2517	-44.8041	-0.72379
15	14	2023-05-2	7	3	1.87655	-0.78529	0.607312	0.333319	0.284769	-49.915	-49.6785	-0.11826
16	15	2023-05-2	8	1	0.442583	0.305827	0.86378	0.080915	0.576903	-66.9353	-66.7338	-0.10076
17	16	2023-05-2	8	2	3.345925	2.171968	4.596063	0.553247	0.820282	-69.9683	-63.7664	-3.10095
18	17	2023-05-2	9	1	0.442583	0.266457	0.808661	0.15002	0.498793	-67.0624	-66.8885	-0.08699
19	18	2023-05-2	9	2	1.239231	-5.52587	-2.00039	0.169713	1.279471	-53.1914	-44.9026	-4.14441
20	19	2023-05-2	9	3	1.646407	3.611096	0.339855	0.698788	0.421592	-49.6364	-46.4791	-1.57866
21	20	2023-05-2	9	4	3.416738	-1.07606	0.040453	1.217538	3.948152	-71.0491	-70.7708	-0.13914
22	21	2023-05-2	10	1	0.442583	0.266457	0.840157	0.07747	0.548294	-66.9891	-66.8026	-0.09322
23	22	2023-05-2	10	2	3.646881	-0.27798	1.535321	0.649538	0.164773	-70.2427	-69.6585	-0.29214
24	23	2023-05-2	11	1	0.442583	0.282205	0.871654	0.093432	0.5712	-67.0742	-66.8728	-0.10073
25	24	2023-05-2	11	2	1.416265	-3.43321	-2.34994	0.462972	0.383178	-49.1707	-45.0165	-2.0771
26	25	2023-05-2	11	3	1.770331	3.3172	1.148994	0.904048	0.371141	-50.6871	-47.7294	-1.47888
27	26	2023-05-2	11	4	3.310518	1.065232	1.485827	0.843964	1.29415	-69.4317	-68.6295	-0.40109
28	27	2023-05-2	12	1	0.442583	0.290079	0.753543	0.087398	0.471811	-67.3496	-67.1931	-0.07824
29	28	2023-05-2	12	2	1.310045	-4.37823	-1.94626	0.184827	0.476519	-51.6313	-46.1217	-2.75482
30	29	2023-05-2	12	3	1.646407	1.320262	2.597375	1.016033	0.561122	-48.6247	-46.5872	-1.01873
31	30	2023-05-2	13	1	0.442583	0.250709	0.824409	0.108307	0.512816	-66.9994	-66.8212	-0.0891
32	31	2023-05-2	13	2	1.416265	-4.80666	-1.26108	0.356619	1.201946	-51.9681	-46.0415	-2.96332
33	32	2023-05-2	13	3	1.823441	1.132598	2.621435	1.668869	0.331078	-48.39	-46.4329	-0.97856
34	33	2023-05-2	14	1	0.442583	0.290079	0.816535	0.123047	0.50814	-66.9683	-66.788	-0.09011
35	34	2023-05-2	14	2	1.186121	-3.09817	-1.92544	1.545704	1.768548	-57.4296	-54.2362	-1.59672
36	35	2023-05-2	14	3	1.823441	-1.13862	1.918898	0.904048	0.207694	-43.7166	-42.5217	-0.59744
37	36	2023-05-2	14	4	3.469848	-2.82691	-4.79989	1.459403	0.046297	-69.9059	-62.4586	-3.72364
38	37	2023-05-2	15	1	0.442583	0.329449	0.855906	0.078345	0.570722	-67.2558	-67.0539	-0.10093
39	38	2023-05-2	15	2	1.805727	-2.18761	1.736045	0.15002	0.180878	-44.3888	-42.5169	-0.93594

- Open excel file
- There needs to be ~3000 pings
- Filtering the data
 - Select all values in the column that does not include the header (i.e. X Angle)
 - Right click > Filter > Filter by selected cell values
 - Sometimes this will automatically filter the values, but this will be needed to get edited

- Select Number Filters > Between...

- Set the values to -3 and 3
- Hit OK

*** Repeat these steps for the Y angle as well, the count number should decrease by a couple hundred.

- Once all the data has been filtered copy all cells under the Target Strength column and past in a new sheet
- Now calculate the 95 percentile using this equation =PERCENTILE (array, 0.95)
 - Array : select all values pasted onto new page
- 95 percentiles will then be compared to the calibration sphere tables

Calibration sphere expected values can also be calculated using the Standard Sphere Target Strength Calculator from NOAA found at: <https://www.fisheries.noaa.gov/data-tools/standard-sphere-target-strength-calculator>

2.9.4. Echoview calibration offset calculation

A more detailed calibration can be performed in Echoview software and results of this calibration provide both TS and Sv offset values which are required to update .ecs files for proper analysis of echogram data. Detailed information on how to perform calibrations in Echoview can be found online using the Calibration Assistant -

https://support.echoview.com/WebHelp/How_To/Calibrate_Echosounders/Calibrating_an_echosounder.htm

Step by step Echoview calibration instructions are also provided in the Echoview Learner Guide document available from Echoview. We have also provided completed EV calibration files as templates from before and after our survey. See data availability statement for Dryad link to required files. Files located in Lancaster_et_al._Echoview_Templates_and_Scripts-20250521T190818Z-1-001.zip\Echoview_Analysis_Files\Calibration_files.

Use files:

- Cal_echoview_38_startsurvey.EV
- Cal_echoview_200_startsurvey.EV
- Deep_Cal_echoview_38_final.EV
- Deep_Cal_echoview_200_final.EV

Full settings used for calibration are visible by right clicking on ?? in the dataflow tab of the calibration templates and looking under Variable Properties:

The screenshot displays the Echoview software interface. On the left, a dataflow diagram shows a central purple node labeled 'Fileset 1: Channel 2 (38 kHz)'. Three arrows point from this node to three other nodes: a blue node 'Fileset 1: Sv split beam pings (channel 2)', a green node 'Fileset 1: TS split beam pings (channel 2)', and a red node 'Fileset 1: position pings (channel 2)'. Arrows from the green and red nodes point to a final green node 'Single target detection - split beam (method 2) 38'. A red box labeled 'Parameter 1' has an arrow pointing to the 'Fileset 1: Channel 2 (38 kHz)' node. On the right, a 'Filesets' window shows a table with columns for Name, Start date/time, and End date/time. Below it, a 'Variable Properties - Single target detection - split beam (method 2) 38' dialog box is open. The dialog box has tabs for Data, Filter Targets, Echogram Display, Grid, Analysis, Calibration, Lines, Regions, and Single Target Detection. The 'Single Target Detection' tab is active, showing various parameters for 'General parameters', 'Beam compensation', 'Exclusion', and 'Line Exclusion'. The 'General parameters' section includes fields for 'TS threshold (compensated TS) (dB re 1m2):' (set to 52.00), 'Pulse length determination level (dB re 1W):' (6.00), 'Minimum normalized pulse length:' (0.50), and 'Maximum normalized pulse length:' (1.50). The 'Beam compensation' section includes 'Beam compensation model:' (BioSonics) and 'Maximum beam compensation (dB re 1m2):' (6.00). The 'Exclusion' section includes 'Maximum standard deviation of:' (0.600), 'Minor-axis angles (degrees):' (0.600), and 'Major-axis angles (degrees):' (0.600). The 'Line Exclusion' section includes 'Exclude targets above line:' (Min analysis range) and 'Exclude targets below line:' (Max analysis range). Buttons for OK, Cancel, Apply, and Help are at the bottom of the dialog box.

NOTE: .ecs files must be updated with correct sound speed and absorption coefficient values based on water temperature and depth of calibration sphere at location where calibration occurred. See Section 3 – Echoview Annotation Protocol (bullet 6 - Calculating Sound speed and Absorption coefficients for .ecs files) for details on how to update .ecs files.

We have provided an Echoview template file called Nootka_multi.EV (available in folder Echoview_Analysis_Files) which will set up echograms with the same setting we used. The template file must be saved at the following path on the computer you use for analysis:
C:\Users\Public\Documents\Echoview Software\Echoview 14.0\Templates

3. Data annotation

3.1. Event Measure Annotation Protocol

The following protocol is designed for the annotation of ROV videos collected in Nootka Sound in a paired echosounder/ROV video survey. Videos will be annotated in SeaGIS EventMeasure software which requires a subscription. Contact SeaGIS directly for quotes.

NOTE: The BlueROV records .mp4 video files and depth/temp data as a separate associated (.ass) file. In order to load both video data and .ass data (depth, temperature, etc...) into EventMeasure as a single file we needed to create new MP4 files using VLC software. We used the record feature in VLC to create new merged video files following these steps: https://www.fonepaw.com/recorder/record-screen-and-video-with-vlc.html?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiAxKy5BhBbEiwAYiW--w8ZZga79CLK_M6H26G_Bov9957TLCbWKzTp4IHDWq2hrkZJUPDKmRoCugsQAvD_BwE

Items to record:

- Fish species (full Latin names) and count
- Depth
- Substrate, rugosity, and slope at time of fish annotations
- Habitat classification points to be completed every 15 seconds.

Detailed Annotation Step by Step Guide

1. Open EventMeasure software
2. Set File Directory: Picture>Set Picture Directory>Select correct folder where your video files are saved (all videos must be in the same folder).
3. Add columns to Information Field Table (you should only need to do this once): Measurement > Information Fields > Edit Field Names (These fields aren't very important for your work - they should look like this)

Information field names

File

Heading	Name	
Field heading 1	OpCode	
Field heading 2	TapeReader	
Field heading 3	Depth	
Field heading 4	Comment	
Field heading 5	✓	
Field heading 6	✓	
Field heading 7	✓	
Field heading 8	✓	
Field heading 9	✓	
Field heading 10	✓	
Field heading 11	✓	
Field heading 12	✓	

4. Add columns to Attributes Table: Measurement> Attributes > Attribute headers

Attribute headers

File

Attribute	Name	
Attribute name 1	Family	
Attribute name 2	Genus	
Attribute name 3	Species	
Attribute name 4	Code	
Attribute name 5	Number	
Attribute name 6	Stage	
Attribute name 7	Activity	
Attribute name 8	✓ Depth	
Attribute name 9	✓ Sub_Slope	
Attribute name 10	✓ Notes	

5. Load species (species_Lancaster_2022.txt) text files: Measurement> Attributes > edit/load species files (Here you can load in the species text file located in folder odata\Event_Measure_Files).
6. Load Videos for Point Annotations: Picture> Load picture. Select the first transect video you want to annotate.
7. Fill out Information Field Table for specific site: Measurement > Information Fields > Edit Field Values NOTE: This info not very important for this project, just fill out like screenshot below.

Information field values	
File	
Field	Data
OpCode	✓ ROV
TapeReader	✓ Darienne
Depth	✓ NA
Comment	✓ NA
	✓
	✓
	✓
	✓
	✓
	✓
	✓

8. Point Annotations: at this point you should be ready to start annotating video files. Select Play movie, select Play back (you can increase the playback rate with the up and down arrows to make it play faster), when a fish enters select close player and update position. Right click on fish/animals and select add point to start a new point annotation. NOTE: Make a point selection as soon as you're on bottom and about to start annotation, under Notes write Start. Leave all other fields blank.

Substrate Annotations: Create a substrate point as soon as ROV is on bottom to classify the depth, slope, rugosity, and substrate. Substrate codes: M = Mud, S = Sand, P = Pebble, C = Cobble, B = Boulder, R = Bedrock. see classification guide for info on substrate classes <https://www.usgs.gov/media/images/substrate-classification-0> . Slope categories (0 = 0 degrees, 30= >0-30 degrees, 60= 30-60 degrees, 90=60-90 degrees). Rugosity categories (1 – substrate 0-25cm (majority fine substrate or small crevices in pebbles or cobble), 2 – substrate >25cm and <50cm (small boulders and bedrock cracks), 3 – substrate >50cm and <75cm (large boulders or large cracks in bedrock). Example coding (B_30_2 = Boulder habitat with >0-30 degree slope and >25cm and <50cm rugosity. S_0_1 = sand habitat with 0 degree slope and <25cm rugosity). Be careful of typos while coding slope and substrate and rugosity. Make a new substrate/slope/rugosity annotation every 15 seconds. All fish annotations should also have substrate type and slope and rugosity recorded within their annotations so we know what kind of habitat they were found in.

Field of View (FOV) Annotations: Take a screenshot every 30 seconds (right click image and save as JPEG). Save files in folder you create named FOV on harddrive. Ensure site name is associated with each file. Try to get screenshots with view of lasers on bottom so we can determine average FOV of video later. If lasers are not visible in all screenshots that's fine as long as it's visible a few times on the screen shots.

Export interesting video clips: You can export video clips of interesting activities by right clicking on image and selecting export video. If something interesting happens (greenling chasing laser, interesting unique species, etc...) you can export a short clip (make sure site name is associated with file and give description - e.g. NS24_T2_ROV_20230814_KGlaserchase.mp4). Note: it can take a while to export clips so keep them short.

Ending Annotations: Make a final point annotation with a note that says End once the ROV stops forward motion and heads into water column. Leave all other fields blank.

Point Annotations:

Items to Record

Attributes table window view

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Attributes - Point" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The window contains several input fields, each with a label on the left and a corresponding input area on the right. The fields are: "Family" (dropdown menu), "Genus" (dropdown menu), "Species" (dropdown menu, currently highlighted in blue), "Code" (text input), "Number" (text input with the value "1"), "Stage" (dropdown menu with the value "AD"), "Activity" (dropdown menu with the value "Passing"), "Depth" (dropdown menu), "Sub_Slope" (dropdown menu), and "Notes" (dropdown menu). At the bottom of the window, there are two buttons: "OK" and "Cancel".

Family

- Fish: select Family name from scroll down menu (see list of common species below)
- Mammals: Full Latin names of harbour seals, sea lions and otters available. Use general mammal option for any other unexpected mammals and specify common name in comments section.
- Invertebrates: there are options for crabs and other invertebrates but we're not really interested in annotating these. Only record if it's something really interesting or unusual happening, otherwise ignore inverts.
- Bird: on the off chance a diving bird is seen use this option

Genus: Select genus name from scroll down menu.

Species: Select species name from scroll down menu. TIME SAVING TIP: if you know the species name you can type this before selecting Genus and Family and those items will auto fill. (e.g. type maliger and *Sebastes* and *Scorpaenidae* will auto fill). NOTE: For juvenile rockfish mark any juveniles with a black spot on their dorsal fin as Black Rockfish (*Sebastes melanops*). These juveniles could be Black,

Yellowtail or Canary but I just want an easy way to identify that they have the black spot on dorsal fin. (See photo). Any juveniles without a visible dorsal spot should just be identified to the genus level.

Code: will auto fill if this information is available. These codes are from the Integrated Taxonomic Integration System

https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=1155410#null

NOTE: some of the general categories I created like Mammal have fake codes so disregard these numbers.

Number: Use this option for schools of fish (i.e.. anything over 10 fish that makes it difficult to track individuals). Specify approximate number in school (E.g. 25 = 25 fish in school). NOTE: If a school lingers in frame for a long time make a new point annotation every 5 seconds and estimate numbers. See Activity section for how to classify pelagic schools.

Stage: Specify AD for Adult, J for Juvenile if it is possible to tell their life stage. NOTE: there is an option for Male or Female specification as well. Use this only for Kelp Greenling as they are sexually dimorphic. For Adult Kelp Greenling record only sex and disregard life stage (e.g. AD or J). If it is clearly a juvenile Kelp Greenling sex cannot be determined so juvenile life stage can be selected.

Activity:

Chase Other - Use this item to record when fish are chasing lasers. If you have already made a point for the fish and then it begins to chase the lasers later and you need to make a new point indicate this in the notes section by writing recount.

Example:

Attributes - Point	
Family	Hexagrammidae
Genus	Hexagrammos
Species	decagrammus
Code	167110
Number	1
Stage	M
Activity	Chase other
Depth	71.8
Sub_Slope	B_60
Notes	recount

OK Cancel

Scavenging - Use this item to mark pelagic schools (i.e.. any schools that occupy areas predominantly more than 2m off the bottom). If the schools are continuously present make a new count estimate point every 5 seconds. If you can't tell what species the pelagic schools are write a note that indicates either small like juvenile rockfish, perch, etc.. or large like yellowtail rockfish (use codes: small pelagics, or large pelagics). If you have multiple comments, separate with underscores. Example:

Shortform codes for annotating schools of fish:

SP = Small pelagic

SP_C = Small pelagic continued

BP = Big pelagic

BP_C = Big pelagic continued

SB = Small Benthic (set activity to passing not scavenging for bottom dwelling schools)

SB_C = Small benthic continued (set activity to passing not scavenging for bottom dwelling schools)

Note: If unsure of fish ID, identify to lowest confident level (e.g. rockfish/Sebastes - we can go over these together.)

When the ROV begins to ascend or stops forward momentum in shallow water make final annotation by writing End in notes field. Leave all other fields empty.

Saving files: You can save a file as an EMObs file by selecting Measurements>Save. Use the following naming convention (NootkaROV_20230828.EMObs) Make sure you back up the EMObs file you create each time you do annotations by saving to both the computer and harddrive. Change date in save name each time you finish annotating in case files become corrupted, this will give a form of version control. Continue to annotate all video files using the same measurement file. The File Name column will allow you to separate data by site later. To load the next site for annotation go to Picture>Load

Picture> select next video> Open> Ok. You can always remove the previously annotated files if the software is starting to run slowly.

Exporting csvs: Measurement>measurement summaries>point measurements> file> save data at txt file > save as .csv to export.

3.2. ImageJ: Field of View Measurements:

Save a transect image every 30 seconds once annotation has begun. Try to get image with lasers visible when possible but this is not always possible. Save all jpeg images to site specific folder.

To calculate mean field of view per transect open ImageJ software. File>Open> select first FOV image from transect folder.

Select line tool

 ImageJ

Draw line between laser dots

Select Analyze>Set Scale> Change known distance to 10 and unit of length to cm.

Draw line across entire FOV, hold down shift key to make line straight.

Select Analyze>Measure and copy down length into FOV Calculator spreadsheet.

Area	Mean	Min	Max	Angle	Length
12.339	66.132	50	90.667	0	153.920

Repeat this process to measure the height of the ROV frame from top to bottom. Repeat measurement steps for all FOV images (NOTE: set scale must be recalculated for each image) then calculate mean FOV and Standard Deviation for the full transect and save value to Transect Mean FOV tab.

correct file location by right clicking and selecting browse for file.

5. To apply template to your own data, load a new transect file into file sets window using add button. Remove NS24 file. Save file as transect name + analysis (e.g NS01_T1_Biosonic_20230810_094445_analysis.EV).
6. We also provide a calibration .ecs file called Multifrequency_analysis_Template_wCalVals.ecs. If there is a red X beside the file name in the Filesets window (at bottom) you need to manually navigate to the correct folder where the .ecs file is saved using the three dots button (...). This calibration file contains values from our data calibration. For your data you must create a new .ecs file with transect name + analysis by selecting the three dots (...) at bottom of filesets window. Save .ecs files to same folder as EV files.

NOTES:

- Calibration offsets from our study are included in this file. You must update calibration offsets with correct values from your study.
- To save a .ecs file you need to manually type .ecs at the end of the text file or it will not save correctly
- To open the new .ecs file select ... and open up the correct .ecs file. This will automatically update your echograms with the new calibration values.

Calculating Sound speed and Absorption coefficients for .ecs files

- Use sonar calculator (Help>Sonar Calculator) to find Sound speed and Absorption Coefficient for specific transect. Input mean temperature from transect and mean depth (calculated in R from StarOddi data – see Section 4 - R analysis for more details) and transducer frequency, leave other values as is.

- Calculate values for both 201.34kHz and 38kHz. For sound speed use the (Mackenzie 1981) value.
- Input sound speed and absorption coefficient values in transect specific .ecs file (Filesets Window>Edit).

```

SourceCal (channel 1)
AbsorptionCoefficient = 0.050425 # (decibels per meter) [0.000000..100.000000]
CalibrationOffsetSv = 1.893 # (decibels) [-999.900..999.900]
CalibrationOffsetTs = 1.006 # (decibels) [-999.900..999.900]
# Dt4PowerSetting = 0.00 # (decibels) [-100.00..0.00]
# Frequency = 201.34 # (kilohertz) [0.01..10000.00]
MajorAxis3dbBeamAngle = 6.21 # (degrees) [0.00..360.00]
MajorAxisAngleOffset = -0.20 # (degrees) [-9.99..9.99]
MinorAxis3dbBeamAngle = 6.54 # (degrees) [0.00..360.00]
MinorAxisAngleOffset = -0.14 # (degrees) [-9.99..9.99]
# PulseDuration = 0.400 # (milliseconds) [0.001..200.000]
# ReceiveSensitivity = -46.30 # (decibels) [-1000.00..1000.00]
SoundSpeed = 1485.35 # (meters per second) [1400.00..1700.00]
# SourceLevel = 221.500 # (decibels) [-1000.000..1000.000]
# TvgrangeCorrection = BioSonics # [None, BySamples, SimradEx500, SimradEx60, BioSonics, Kaijo, PulseLength, Ex500Forced, SimradEK80, Standard]
# TwoWayBeamAngle = -21.229721 # (decibels re 1 steradian) [-99.000000..11.000000]

SourceCal (channel 2)
AbsorptionCoefficient = 0.009321 # (decibels per meter) [0.000000..100.000000]
CalibrationOffsetSv = 3.580 # (decibels) [-999.900..999.900]
CalibrationOffsetTs = 1.901 # (decibels) [-999.900..999.900]
# Dt4PowerSetting = 0.00 # (decibels) [-100.00..0.00]
# Frequency = 38.00 # (kilohertz) [0.01..10000.00]
MajorAxis3dbBeamAngle = 9.95 # (degrees) [0.00..360.00]
MajorAxisAngleOffset = -0.34 # (degrees) [-9.99..9.99]
MinorAxis3dbBeamAngle = 10.35 # (degrees) [0.00..360.00]
MinorAxisAngleOffset = -0.23 # (degrees) [-9.99..9.99]
# PulseDuration = 0.400 # (milliseconds) [0.001..200.000]
# ReceiveSensitivity = -39.20 # (decibels) [-1000.00..1000.00]
SoundSpeed = 1485.35 # (meters per second) [1400.00..1700.00]
# SourceLevel = 212.300 # (decibels) [-1000.000..1000.000]
# TvgrangeCorrection = BioSonics # [None, BySamples, SimradEx500, SimradEx60, BioSonics, Kaijo, PulseLength, Ex500Forced, SimradEK80, Standard]
# TwoWayBeamAngle = -17.620600 # (decibels re 1 steradian) [-99.000000..11.000000]

```

Absorption Coefficients should be different for 200 and 38 frequencies, sound speed should be the same. Make sure you input values for the correct transducer (channel 1 = 200, channel 2 = 38). Save changes (File>Save).

Repick lines on template

9. Open 200kHz and 38kHz Sv echogram tabs by clicking on operator boxes (Sv split beam pings (channel 1 and 2)) in dataflow tab.
10. Repick bottom line (lime green line) on 200kHz Sv Echogram. Select echogram, select Bottom line in tool bar.

Right click in 200 echogram and select recalculate line (line pick from variable).

When line appears right click on line>line properties>Source>Properties and match settings to:

Hit apply>Ok. Right click 200 echogram and select recalculate line (line pick from variable) again.

11. Redraw bottom line in 200 echogram to eliminate any errors. Pay special attention to any rhythmic looking dips in bottom line (this is likely side to side wave effects on boat and must be manually smoothed - this may impact rugosity values but needs to be done).

12. Repick Large deadzone buffer line (orange line) on 38kHz Sv Echogram. Select echogram, select Deadzone line in tool bar.

Right click in 38 echogram and select recalculate line (line pick from variable).

When line appears right click on line>line properties>Source>Properties and match settings to:

Hit apply>Ok. Right click 38 echogram and select recalculate line (line pick from variable again).

- The discrimination level is the most important part, the deadzone buffer having a lower (-70 vs -90) value will mean that the deadzone sits above that of the bottom line.

13. Redraw deadzone line in 38 echogram to eliminate any errors. (NOTE: example site has uncharacteristically large interference areas (blue hump) due to side lobe interference).

Ensure no strong bottom echoes are above the deadzone buffer line.

Manual Buffer selection: For manual buffer selection create new EV file with manual buffer in name. Edit Large deadzone line to include any areas of suspected fish backscatter (defined as near bottom echoes showing separation from the detected bottom at a -55dB threshold). Adjust threshold settings in Echoview to -55 and examine if suspected fish school is still visible and has a visible gap between bottom and school. Draw around suspected fish schools using the repick line tool. Proceed with analysis steps outlined below to export line and NASC data.

1m Buffer selection: For 1m buffer selection create new EV file with manual buffer in name. Delete existing Deadzone buffer line in dataflow tab. Create new deadzone line using an offset from the bottom line (-1m will apply line 1m above deadzone).

Proceed with analysis steps outlined below to export line and NASC data.

Remove extra echogram data from before or after transect with ping subset tool

14. In dataflow tab right click Ping subset remove nontransect>variable properties>ping subset. Set Range to first ping in transect (if there is no start transect marker this will be ping 0) If there is a start transect marker input correct ping number from beginning of marker.

Make sure there are exactly 5 vertical grid sections. If there is extra at the start or end of transect check transect depth values from datasheets and ping subset accordingly to make a 100m long transect. NOTE: this is only required if you are binning your data into smaller distance bins (e.g. 20m) for our analysis we decided to use 100m transect data only as 20m data was too short for meaningful comparison to ROV transects.

Example: Transect is too long, over 100m, extra chunk at beginning without start transect marker.

Count number of pings in end chunk to get rough estimate of where to reset pings to. In this example reset to:

Exporting Data

15. Three different Rocky Reef Fish Zone lines (5, 10, 15m – pink/purple lines) are available in the template. Data can be exported between the deadzone buffer of choice and the Rocky Reef Fish Zone line of choice (e.g. 1m deadzone buffer to 10m Rocky Reef Fish Zone).
16. Right click in 38kHz Ping subset remove off transect echogram. Variable properties> Analysis. Match settings to:

This will export only data between the deadzone line and the 5m Rockfish Zone.

17. Ensure filename will be exported: Click on view>EV file properties>Export

- Under analysis variables to export select Analysis export>EV_filename

18. Export data:

Save under to desired folder. We recommend different folders for each variation on deadzone and Rocky Reef Fish Zone (e.g. Transect 1\1mDZ\100x15 for Transect 1, 1m deadzone buffer, 100m transect with 15m Rocky Reef Fish Zone).

Suggested file naming convention: File name + export parameters - (e.g. NS34_T1_Biosonic_20230816_094445_1mDZ_100x15.csv).

19. For optional 20m binned data open exported file and ensure there are 0 values for layer and that there are 5 intervals. If there are extra layers ensure that deadzone and bottom line do not overlap and reexport. If there are still extra layers you can manually delete them, keep all layer 0 value

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	Process_ID	Interval	Layer	Sv_mean	NASC	Height_me	Depth_me	Layer_dep	Layer_dep	Ping_S	Ping_E	Dist_M	Date_M	Time_M	Lat_M	Lon_M	Nois
2	368	1	0	-999	0	14.99868	45.54132	-66.67253	53.87946	0	45	9.99852	20230816	09:45:08.1	49.75509	-126.6278	
3	368	2	0	-89.30163	0.759335	15.00045	43.51849	-66.67253	53.87946	46	90	29.79886	20230816	09:45:23.6	49.75526	-126.6278	
4	368	3	0	-78.57622	8.973035	14.99925	39.72402	-66.67253	53.87946	91	137	49.752	20230816	09:45:39.2	49.75543	-126.6278	
5	368	4	0	-82.77181	3.415384	15.00129	35.367	-66.67253	53.87946	138	185	70.49066	20230816	09:45:55.0	49.75562	-126.6278	
6	368	5	0	-74.01494	26.26251	15.35815	28.38456	-66.67253	53.87946	186	233	90.4179	20230816	09:46:11.3	49.75579	-126.6278	
7																	
8																	
9																	

20. If you are binning data into 20m or other smaller chunks follow these exports steps: Repeat export process for 20x10, and 20x5 data by changing the analysis tab in variable properties to the correct Rockfish Zone line. Ensure you save to the correct folder each time and add the Site ID column to each .csv file.

Exporting bottom and deadzone lines for option 20m bins.

21. Select vertical tool:

- Highlight 20m section of transect.

Right click selection:

Save in appropriate 20mlines folder as: NS34_T1_Biosonic_20230816_094445_Bottom_1.line.csv.

NOTE: add interval number at end of filename (e.g. 1, 2, 3...). (Can load full line segments and split up by 20m in R if you'd rather).

Open .csv and add Site ID column and Interval column:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	Site	Interval	Ping_date	Ping_time	Ping_milli:	Latitude	Longitude	Position_s
2	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:31	441	49.75535	-126.6278	1
3	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:31	779	49.75535	-126.6278	1
4	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:32	117	49.75536	-126.6278	1
5	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:32	454	49.75536	-126.6278	1
6	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:32	792	49.75536	-126.6278	1
7	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:33	130	49.75537	-126.6278	1
8	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:33	468	49.75537	-126.6278	1
9	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:33	805	49.75537	-126.6278	1
10	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:34	143	49.75538	-126.6278	1
11	NS34	1	2023-08-16	09:45:34	482	49.75538	-126.6278	1

22. Repeat for Deadzone line segments. Export Deadzone, Slope, and Bottom line segments for each of the five 20m transect chunks.

Exporting 100m line segments:

23. Repeat export process for full transect data (e.g. 100mx15mRockfish zone, 100x10, 100x5). To do this remove 20m grid lines with variable properties>Grid: Settings should be:

Final .csv exports from each Transect 1 file:

100m exports

- 100mx15m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- 100mx10m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- 100mx5m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- Bottom line export
- Deadzone line export x 3 (one for each type of deadzone line if comparing)

20m exports

- 20mx15m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- 20mx10m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- 20mx5m Rocky Reef Fish Zone
- Bottom line exports (one file for each of the 5 intervals)
- Deadzone line exports (one file for each of the 5 intervals x 3 for each deadzone buffer)

Transect 3 Exports: To check if NASC values change from beginning to end of your survey you can repeat the following steps on the Transect 3 (pass 3) echograms and export NASC values of interest. We looked at NASC values from 10m rocky reef fish zone (RFZ) and 1m deadzone buffer.

3.4. Details on Echoview multifrequency analysis template

The following information explains the rationale behind the operator selections we used in our multifrequency analysis templates. Most of this information is also provided as sticky notes within the multifrequency template dataflow tab.

Bottom pick and Deadzone pick: Used Maximum Sv algorithm. This works by finding the sample within a ping with the strongest backscattering strength and setting the line to the first point before that values that matches the discrimination level. Biggest setting is the discrimination level which says where within a single ping (see ping graph) it will set the line. For bottom it was set to -50 dB, for deadzone it was set to -70. This was based on visual inspection of echogram and how well these settings seemed to match where the actual bottom and deadzones are. (See help doc. Line properties - Maximum Sv for more details).

Background Noise Removal: Set to 40 pings by 10m vertical. This is based on sensitivity to grid cell analysis done by De Robertis et al. 2007 where 40x10m stabilized variability and decreased overall noise estimates. Too small of vertical extent can cause errors in noise calculation. SNR is set to 10 as a default based on De Robertis 2007. -125 is default max noise based on De Robertis for single beam (good for split too, not good for multibeam). This is max noise expected but could be higher than this, need to evaluate echograms visually to make sure this setting works.

De Robertis, Alex, and Ian Higginbottom. "A Post-Processing Technique to Estimate the Signal-to-Noise Ratio and Remove Echosounder Background Noise." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 64, no. 6 (September 1, 2007): 1282–91. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsm112>.

>-70 38: This operator creates a boolean echogram with true and false values. All cells with an Sv value greater than -70dB are True. This is applied to both 38 and 200 frequencies. -70 is a good range for excluding most low backscattering items in water column while still preserving small values for juvenile fish/krill etc...

Rocky Reef Fish Zone Lines: Virtual rockfish zone lines are used to create exclusion zones during grid export in ping subset echogram to only look at Sv values in the 15, 10 or 5 m closest to the bottom. 15m semi-pelagic rockfish zone based off: Parker, S. J., J. M. Olson, P. S. Rankin, and J. S. Malvitch. "Patterns in Vertical Movements of Black Rockfish *Sebastes Melanops*." *Aquatic Biology* 2, no. 1 (March 13, 2008): 57–65. <https://doi.org/10.3354/ab00036>.

Impulse Noise Removal: Applied to 200 only as more likely to occur at higher frequency. If you see impulse noise in 38 it can be applied here too. Algorithm looks for:

The Impulse noise removal operator identifies and adjusts sample values that are significantly higher than those of surrounding samples at the same depth.

Based on the combination of settings applied, it can be used to adjust the value of samples that are affected by impulse noise such as interference from other sonars (which manifest as short 'flecks' on an echogram). Care is required to prevent it from adjusting good data. The operator is based on the "impulsive noise (IN)" algorithm and definitions described in: Ryan, Tim E., Ryan A. Downie, Rudy J. Kloser, and Gordon Keith. "Reducing Bias Due to Noise and Attenuation in Open-Ocean Echo Integration Data." *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 72, no. 8 (October 1, 2015): 2482–93. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsv121>.

Resample 3pingx.5m: This resampling creates new cells based on a weighted mean of 3 pings by .5m vertically. This resampling is useful for ensuring Sv/NASC values come from solid fish aggregations rather than highly variable fringe areas. For our data 3pings is ~0.5m horizontally so our grid cells are the weighted mean of .5x.5m grids. This works well to remove fringe areas at the edges of aggregations where there are likely very few fish or large quantities of krill. Stop range set to 100m to match our end echosounding range. Number of datapoints set to 200 to create .5m vertical grids. Echograms were visually inspected while selecting these values to make sure they seemed to match what was happening in echogram.

Match Ping Times: This operator selects pings from the first operand in such a way as to match the times of the pings in the second operand. The resulting variable will have one ping for every ping in the second operand. The data for that ping will however come from the ping in the first operand with the nearest ping time. A ping time difference less than Maximum acceptable time difference indicates a successful match. If no successful match is found, then the ping from the second operand does not appear in the resulting echogram.

Mask dB Diff 200-38 (>-70): This creates an echogram with only the filtered values greater than -70dB. I have created a colour scale that shows where euphausids and fish are likely to be separated at the 2dB different mark. Greener values will be classified as Euphausids.

Fish dB Diff Range 200-38: This is the most important step as it subtracts the 38 frequency values from the 200 values and keeps all values with a decibel range from -16 to 2dB (this is based on Sato 2015 study from our region - very reliable for this area and commonly used.)

The range for the Euph dB Diff Range 200-38 is from 2-30dB. So if a target has a value of -64 at 38kHz and -60 at 200kHz it will be classed as Euphausids (-60 minus -64 = 4dB). If it has a value of -40 at 38 and -50 at 200 it will be classified as fish (-50 minus -40 = -10dB).

Sato, Mei, John K. Horne, Sandra L. Parker-Stetter, and Julie E. Keister. "Acoustic Classification of Coexisting Taxa in a Coastal Ecosystem." *Fisheries Research* 172 (December 1, 2015): 130–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fishres.2015.06.019>.

Ping subset remove off transect : This is an easy way to remove start or end data that is not part of the 100m transect. You can look at specific ping numbers within echogram to create cut off points to get rid of data that should not be analyzed.

4. Data cleaning and analysis in R

We performed all data cleaning and analysis operation in R version 4.3.3.. We created a project within R and used github for version control and data backups. All required scripts for data cleaning and analysis are provided at the Dryad link in the data availability statement. Original data has not been provided due to the sensitive rocky reef fish location information it contains. Original data is available upon request from Ha'oom Fisheries Society at info@haoom.ca and consent of the Mowachaht/Muchalaht First Nation will be obtained before data is provided to interested parties. If data is shared, we will provide all original data for R processing in the folder odata (original data). Processed dataframes within scripts are exported to the folder wdata (working data). Figures created during analysis are saved to the folder figures and all R scripts are found in the folder scripts. We

recommend downloading all four folders and saving them to your project directory. Scripts are numbered sequentially and running through them in order will ensure all required dataframes are loaded.

Script descriptions:

1_install_packages.R

A short function used to install and load all packages.

2_depth_temp.R

Clean StarOddi depth and temperature logger data.

3_Nootka_time.R

Load field datasheets to calculate survey duration at each site and mean and SD.

4_cleanedcode.R

Primary code for cleaning EventMeasure ROV fish annotations. Substrate and slope data from EventMeasure annotations are calculated. Field of View is calculated from ImageJ analysis results. Average depth and temperature per site is calculated (this information is useful for creating calibration files (.ecs) in Echoview before exporting line and NASC information). Fish abundance and species richness are calculated for multiple species groupings (e.g. all rockfish, all schooling fish, all soft substrate fish). We also provide code on how to bin transect data into smaller (20m) bins. We did not use binned data in our analysis but this could be helpful for performing a binned analysis on future data. We also provide code on how to calculate abundance per subarea which was not used in the publication but is helpful for regional analyses.

5_lines_calculations.R

This script processes exported bottom and deadzone buffer lines from Echoview. All required Echoview lines must be exported before running this script and we recommend saving them in folders with the same names we used for ease of code use (e.g. odata/Transect 1/100mLines/Bottom). We calculate slope using the Great Circle Distance formula for both 20m and 5m slope bins. We also calculate both rugosity metrics (SD Slope and Ratio). We also calculate Deadzone buffer area using bottom and deadzone buffer lines. Code for binned data (20m bins) is also provided but was not used in publication.

6_SV_NASC_datapull.R

This script processes exported NASC values for 5, 10, and 15m rocky reef fish zones (RFZs). All NASC exports must be completed in Echoview before running this code. We recommend saving exports in files with the same path we used (e.g. odata/Transect 1/100x10/1mDZ). Binned 20m code is also provided but was not used in publication.

7_analysis_GLMs_Spearman.R

This script contains the primary analysis code for figures and results reported in the publication. We load in additional habitat variables used in our analysis (e.g. ROV rugosity). We create a main dataframe with all important variables from both ROV and echosounder data. We examine

Spearman's correlations between all echosounder and ROV variables. We run GLM analyses on benthic fish density data with echosounder and ROV variables as predictors. We also run GLMs for all combinations of rocky reef fish zones heights and deadzone buffer methods. We also examine NASC values across different RFZs and deadzone buffer methods and compare Pass 1 NASC values to Pass 3 NASC values.

8_ROV_fish_summary_stats.R

This script creates a summary table of all fish seen with the ROV for a variety of species groupings. Final editing of this table was performed in Microsoft word.

9_Deadzone_height_calculator.R

This script provides a method of calculating theoretical deadzone heights based on max, min, and mean depths, slopes and rugosity levels encountered across echosounder surveys. This formula is reproduced from the paper:

Tušer, Michal, Helge Balk, Tomáš Mrkvička, Jaroslava Frouzová, Martin Čech, Milan Muška, and Jan Kubečka. "Validation of Current Acoustic Dead-Zone Estimation Methods in Lakes with Strongly Sloped Bottoms: Acoustic Dead Zones on Sloped Bottoms." *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* 9, no. 10 (October 2011): 507–14. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lom.2011.9.507>.